

Analytical Evaluation of Status of Gaseous Pollutants with in an Integrated Steel Plant

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A comprehensive analytical study on exposure and intake of different gaseous pollutants from some stationary sources in the coke-oven by-product plant of an integrated steel industry has been carried out.

The coke-oven by-product plant comprises different units like ammonium sulphate plant, benzol recovery and rectification plant, tar distillation plant and sulphuric acid plant. These plants emit different pollutants like sulphur dioxide, ammonia, benzene homologs and aromatic hydrocarbons. The concentration of these pollutants above the permissible limit may cause adverse effect on the health of the workers¹. The permissible exposure limit(ppm) for different pollutants² are : ammonia, 25 ppm; sulphur dioxide, 2; benzene, 10; aromatic hydrocarbons, 5–100 ppm.

Results and Discussion

The coke oven gas coming out from the batteries contains valuable chemicals like tar, ammonia

and benzol, which are recovered and the gas is cleaned in the by-product plant³. The gaseous concentration was measured at the various locations of each plant. Mean time weighted average concentrations are reported in Table 1. Duration of sampling was from 4 to 4.5 h depending on the process of operation at different units. Gaseous concentrations were found to be above the threshold limit value at sulphuric acid and benzol rectification plant. The vulnerable areas identified were pump-house of benzol rectification plant and furnace area of sulphuric acid plant as revealed from the data.

Experimental

The gas concentration was measured by Drager polymer (Dragerwerk AG, Germany). The polymer consisted of a hose pump which continuously sucked air through Drager tubes. The volume of air sucked was calculated by multiplying the constant (0.71 cm³/rev)⁴. The concentration

TABLE 1—GASEOUS POLLUTANT'S DATA AT DIFFERENT SECTION OF THE PLANT

Plant	Air contaminant	No. of observations	Concn. range range ppm	Mean concn. ppm	Std. dev. (s.d)	TLV
Ammonium sulphate plant	Ammonia	19	8–18	13	(2.19)	25
Sulphuric acid plant	Sulphur dioxide	17	3–6.5	4.5*	(1.32)	2
Benzol rectification plant	Benzene	20	15–21.2	17*	(1.58)	10
Tar distillation plant	Aromatic hydrocarbons	17	73–102	92	(7.6)	5–100

*Value exceeded permissible exposure limit.

of the gases and fumes was calculated from the length of the stain on the detector tube and total volume sucked in by the pump. For taking the gas sample from the contaminated area, the pump below was compressed completely and then released in order to draw the air sample through the drager tube where the effective colour change gave the gas concentration (ppm). The suction rate of the pump was 100 cm³ per stroke.

Two types of sampling were performed. (i) Grab sampling was done for instant checking of the gas leakage at the work place and the instrument multigas detector was used for this purpose. (ii) Long hour sampling was carried out with the instrument Drager polymer for determination of the mean value of the gas concentration over the extended period of time. Different work sites were selected and then the instrument Drager polymer was installed for 4-5 h to monitor the time weighted average (TWA) concentration of the gases.

Two types of detector tubes were used for the environment survey : long-term and short-term measurement tubes. Long-term measurement tubes were used in Drager polymer instrument as detailed below : (a) ammonia, 10/a-L; range 10, 100 ppm, (b) benzene, 20/a-L; range, 20-200 ppm, (c) sulphur dioxide, 5/a-L; range, 5-50 ppm,

(d) hydrocarbons, 100/a-L; range, 100-3000 ppm. Short-term measurement tubes were used in Drager multigas detector pump for grab sampling : (a) ammonia, 5/a-L; range, n = 10 strokes 5-70 ppm, (b) benzene, 0.5/a-L; range, 0.5-10 ppm, (c) sulphur dioxide, 1/a; range, n = 10 strokes 1-25 ppm, (d) hydrocarbons, (PAH) 100/ a/L; range, 10-300 ppm.

Conclusion : The evaluation and measurement of gas pollutants will help to control the health hazard in the working environment, which can be achieved through an adequate set of preventive measures⁵. An effective engineering control, provision of personal protective equipments at the work-place and good house-keeping will help to reduce the gases and fumes concentration at the work place and will provide better working environment.

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